

Volume III- 2021

RJBUI

ISSN-2250-1681

RESEARCH JOURNAL OF BERHAMPUR UNIVERSITY

BERHAMPUR UNIVERSITY

BHANJA BIHAR, BERHAMPUR-760007, ODISHA, INDIA

RESEARCH JOURNAL OF BERHAMPUR UNIVERSITY

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Berhampur-760007, Odisha, India

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Published Online: Online Version, Berhampur University

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Linkage between Health Expenditure and Foreign Direct Investment in India

Susanta Kumar Tarai^{1*} Dr. Ashok Bhukta²

^{1,2}Research Scholars, PG Department of Economics, Berhampur University

Email: susant86.trii@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: In fact, India is a population-driven country, that needs to focus on population. Their better livelihood, better sanitation, better health can make a country strong in a mass human capital. Nowadays, India needs more investment in the healthcare sector so that it can have a better health infrastructure. By which India can have the fastest health recovery rate. FDI is the master key for any emerging nation to generate employment, raise productivity.

Materials and Methods: To analyse the study of Linkage between Health Expenditure and Foreign Direct Investment in India from 2000 to 2018, this paper has been considered a fully descriptive model using the secondary data collected from various government sources like the World Bank database and IMF database.

Results: *Since January 2000, FDI is permitted up to 100 per cent under the automatic route in hospitals in India. Regarding challenges faced by this sector, it is found that there are external and domestic factors, which challenge foreign investment, especially Foreign Direct Investment in India's hospital segment.*

Conclusion: FDI has the potential to generate employment, raise productivity, enhance the competitiveness of the domestic economy through transfer of skills and technology, enhance exports and contribute to the long-term economic development of the nations.

Key Words: *FDI, Health, Co-integration test, VECM modal and OLS method*

1. Introduction

India, one of the biggest emerging markets, is currently an important destination for foreign direct investment (FDI). Despite India's potential to become one of the most dominant economies in the world, its economic progress since gaining independence in 1947 has generally been masked by a perception of India being a closed, developing country. However, this perception has changed in the recent past and India is today accepted as one of the most stable and robust economies. The healthcare sector as an industry is expanding rapidly in India and has not been as severely impacted by the economic slowdown as some of the other industries. It comprises hospital services, diagnostic services, diagnostic products, medical devices, medical technology, e-Health service, clinical trial services, and clinical research

organizations. This sector is predominantly privatized with almost 75 to 80 per cent of hospitals being managed by the private sector.

The health care industry in India is mounting fast. This is because people are becoming more conscious of diseases and ailments. They want their health to stay in proper condition and a disease-free existence. A proper investment in the field of medical care will help entrepreneurs deal with health-related affairs. The health care industry in India is thriving with scopes and opportunities each day. Medicines or pharmaceuticals have a significant role in the health care industry. The costs of medicines are increasing per day. As a part of the health care program, a huge section of the population is becoming prone to treatments. These treatments are highly beneficial and curative and they can surely help you have the best health status.

2. Literary Review

The overall footprint of FDI is immense. With the capital base increased in the host economy, the anticipation from FDI is growth increasing through encouraging the inculcation and availability of the latest knowledge and technologies in the process of production. According to (Feenstra & Markusen, 1994) when talking about the new input, the growth of output affects the usage of a wide type of goods which are transitional in the FDI related manufacturing sector. Talking about technologies, FDI is the main source of productivity and innovation. According to (Bhandari, 2007) research, is related to finding out the effect of FDI in income inequality and unemployment especially in Central Asia and Eastern Europe from 1990 to 2002. The result was that FDI has a tremendous effect on the unemployment of the country.

Huang, Yasheng; Tang, Heiwai: The paper builds on the idea that economic reforms in China were designed to attract foreign direct investment (FDI), while the opposite happened in India. We empirically examine how these different reform approaches affect foreign-invested enterprises (FIE) and domestic firms' perceptions about the host country's business environment. Using World Bank survey data, we find that FIEs in India perceive more obstacles to business operations and development relative to domestic firms, especially on issues related to government regulations and legal institutions. **Hossain, Anowar; Hossain Mohammad, Kamal:** The paper examines co-integration and the causal relationship between Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and the economic output or Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in both the short and long run of Bangladesh, Pakistan and India throughout 1972-2008. Three econometric models, viz. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, Engle-Granger two-step co-integration test, Vector error correction mechanism (VECM) have been used. This study also used Granger Causality (GC) to find the directional relationship between FDI and GDP. The results suggest that there is no co-integration between FDI and GDP in both the long and short-run in Bangladesh and India. **Medvedev, Denis:** The

paper investigates the effects of preferential trade agreements (PTAs) on net FDI inflows of member countries using a comprehensive database of PTAs in a panel setting. PTA membership is associated with a positive change in net FDI inflows and FDI gains increase with the market size of PTA partners and their proximity to the host country. The estimated relationship is driven by the developing countries in the sample and agreements signed in the late 1990s-early 2000s, a period when the majority of “deep integration” PTAs have been advanced. **Nunnenkamp, Peter; Mukim Megha:** We assess the location choices of 6020 foreign investors at the level of Indian districts. Employing conditional logit models, we find that clustering of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is driven strongly by herding among investors from both, the same and other countries of origin. However, the behaviour of Nonresident Indians (NRIs) and German investors are strikingly different. **Batra, Ravi and Beladi, Hamid:** Using a Heckscher–Ohlin model, this paper re-examines Robert Mundell’s famous thesis that free trade and unimpeded capital mobility are perfect substitutes. Under very general conditions which, according to many economists, have caused international convergence of factor rewards, we show that in a polluted environment free trade is inferior to free international investment. This happens even though commodity prices and factor rewards are the same with both policies. The practical side of our thesis is that the world will be better off by reducing the volume of trade while removing all barriers to the foreign direct investment that at present hamper the service industries. **Kumar, Anil ; Honnakeri, P.M:** The Indian retail industry is one of the sunrise sectors with huge growth potential. According to the Investment Commission of India, the retail sector is expected to grow almost three times its current levels to \$660 billion by 2015. However, despite the recent developments in retailing and its immense contribution to the economy, retailing continues to be the least evolved industries and the growth of organized retailing in India has been much slower as compared to the rest of the world. Undoubtedly, this dismal situation of the retail sector, despite the ongoing wave of incessant liberalization and globalization, stems from the absence of an FDI encouraging policy in the Indian retail sector. In this context, the present paper attempts to analyse the strategic issues concerning the influx of foreign direct investment in the Indian retail industry. Moreover, with the latest move of the government to allow FDI in the multi-brand and retailing sector, the paper analyzes the reason why foreign retailers are interested in India, the strategies they are adopting to enter India and their prospects in India.

3. Objectives

1. To analyze the FDI in the healthcare sector in India;
2. To understand the economic impact of Foreign Direct Investment in Indian health care sectors;
3. To find out trends of Foreign Direct Investment in health care in India;

4. Background of The Study

The demand for hospital services has been consistently soaring in the country, with every class of the society demanding better quality and standards of healthcare which has resulted in the continuous growth of the healthcare industry. The overall Indian healthcare market is worth around US\$ 100 billion and as per a report of IBEF. Growth in the Healthcare sector is dominated by private players in India, unlike increased government dominance in developed nations. Public spending on healthcare in India is low compared to many countries in the world and as in a recent report, it spends 1.4 per cent of GDP which places India amongst the lowest spending countries (data.worldbank.org). The mismatch between demand for and supply of healthcare services and infrastructure has triggered the emergence of private participation in the provision of healthcare. One recent study has estimated that approximately 54 per cent of the medical institutions, 75 per cent of the hospitals, 51 per cent of the hospital beds, 75 per cent of the dispensaries and 80 per cent of all qualified doctors are in the private sector (Sehgal and Hooda, 2015). All these private entities together provide around 60 per cent inpatient and 80 per cent outpatient care to the Indian population, indicating the presence of a highly privatized healthcare market in India (Sehgal and Hooda, 2015).

4.1 FDI in India's Healthcare Sector Emerges from the Following Facts:

The growing population of India is 1.21 billion as per the Census of 2011 out of which 26.1% is below the poverty line. The healthcare spending in India is less than half of the global average in percentage when compared on a 'per cent of GDP' basis that is 4.13% and is amongst the lowest globally in terms of 'per capita' basis that is 40 US\$ and on 'Purchase Power Parity basis it is 275 US\$. The data on these as per WHO World Health Statistics 2010 by India and other countries are shown in table-1.

Table-1: FDI in India's Healthcare Sector

<i>Country</i>	<i>Healthcare Spend (as a % of GDP)</i>	<i>Healthcare Spend (on a per capita basis in US \$)</i>	<i>Healthcare Spend (on Purchase Power Parity basis in US \$)</i>
India	4.13	40	275
China	4.51	108	935
Pakistan	3.20	32	178
SriLanka	2.61	29	517
Nepal	5.45	38	180
Bangladesh	2.78	33	110
Global	9.72	802	863

Source: WHO World Health Statistics, 2018

4.2 FDI Equity Inflows

Regarding equity inflows into India, where it is shown of all sub-sectors of health care sector like *Drugs & Pharmaceuticals, Hospital & Diagnostic Centers and Medical and Surgical Appliances*. It is depicted that percentage of total inflows into this healthcare sector is 5.17. It has been shown in table-2.

Table-2: FDI equity inflows from April 2000 to December 2020

Sectors	Amount of FDI Inflows		% of Total Inflows
	(in Rs Crore)	In US\$ Million)	
<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	43,439.31	7,034.17	1.35
<i>Drugs & Pharmaceuticals</i>	97,048.25	17,746.39	3.40
<i>Medical and Surgical Appliances</i>	13,404.36	2,177.08	0.42
Grand Total	15389192	2695764	5.17

Source: Fact Sheet on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) from April 2000 to December 2020

Table-3: FDI Inflows in Hospitals and Diagnostic Centers April 2000 to June 2012

period	sector	Amount of FDI inflows	Total FDI Inflows (+)	% with total FDI Inflows(+)	period	sector
		In Rs. crore	In US \$ million	In Rs. crore	In US \$ Milli	
<i>April 2000 To December 2011</i>	<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	5,022.15	1,138.16	713,078.99	158,090.60	0.72
<i>April 2000 To January 2012</i>	<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	5,252.56	1,183.04	723,366.76	160,094.45	0.74
<i>April 2000 To February 2012</i>	<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	5,417.92	1,216.67	734,240.45	162,306.04	0.75
<i>April 2000 To March 2012</i>	<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	6,040.87	1,340.47	775,005.97	170,407.08	0.79
<i>April 2000 To April 2012</i>	<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	6,092.30	1,350.40	784,625.58	172,263	0.78
<i>April,2000 To May 2012</i>	<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	6,300.22	1,388.56	791,854.12	173,590.69	0.80
<i>April 2000 To June 2012</i>	<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	6,340.88	1,395.82	798,825.59	174,834.96	0.80
<i>April 2000 To December 2011</i>	<i>Hospital & Diagnostic Centres</i>	5,022.15	1,138.16	713,078.99	158,090.60	0.72

Source: Compiled from Fact Sheet on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

Table-3 shows that FDI equity inflows received by Hospitals and Diagnostic centres have been increasing positively. The health care sector received Rs.5, 022.15 crores of amount FDI inflows from

April 2000 to December 2011 and it was increased up to Rs.5, 417.92 crores by accounting for 0.75% in total FDI inflows. The growth rate in FDI inflows in the hospital and diagnosis sectors is significantly high during this period. The percentage share of FDI in the hospital and diagnostic sector, in total FDI in India, has been increased from 0.72 in December 2011 to 0.80 in June 2012.

4.3 Reasons to Invest

The Indian pharmaceuticals market is expected to touch USD 55 billion by 2020 from USD 36.7 billion in 2016, growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 15.92 per cent. By 2020, India is likely to be among the top three pharmaceutical markets by incremental growth and the sixth-largest market globally in absolute size. There are over 10,500 manufacturing units and 3,000 pharma companies in India. Over 60,000 generic brands exist across 60 therapeutic categories. India accounts for 20% of global exports in generics, making it the largest provider of generic medicines globally. Indian vaccines are exported to 150 countries. Indian Health Care is expected to rise at a rate of CAGR of 29% during 2015-20 to the US \$280 billion with rising income, greater health awareness, increased prevalence of lifestyle diseases and improved access to insurance. The new National Health Protection Scheme will provide hospitalization cover to over 100 million poor and vulnerable families. Finally, the scheme will provide coverage up to USD 7,700 per family per year for secondary and tertiary care hospitalization. Medical tourism to India is on a rise, primarily due to its expertise in cardiac and orthopaedic procedures, in addition to other specialized areas like neuro-surgeries, cancer treatment and organ transplantation. Drugs worth USD 130 billion are expected to go off-patent between FY17 to FY22, presenting a huge market opportunity for Indian manufacturers. With the increasing penetration of chemists, especially in rural India, OTC drugs will be readily available. Pharma companies have increased spending to tap rural markets and develop better infrastructure. The market share of hospitals is expected to increase from 13.1% in 2009 to 26% in 2020. Over USD 200 Billion is to be spent on medical infrastructure in the next decade. Following the introduction of product patents, several multinational companies are expected to launch patented drugs in India. India's cost of production is significantly lower than that of the USA and almost half of that of Europe. India's total exports of Pharmaceuticals (APIs, Generics and Alternative systems of medicine) during 2016-17 was USD 16.8 billion India has a market share of almost 42% of Generic drugs produced globally, the market size of Africa and the Middle East put together. North America is India's largest export market, receiving over 34% of India's pharmaceuticals exports. Africa is the second largest, receiving over 19% of India's exports. The Indian pharmaceutical industry is largely dominated by generic drugs as the industry earns around 70% of its revenues from the same. India's Pharmaceutical industry has filed the highest number of Drug Master Files (DMFS) with USFDA and by

the end of the year 2016, the number of filings stands at 3,950. India's Abbreviated New Drug Applications (ANDAS) totalling over 4,000 by June 2017.

5. Statement of The Problem

Healthcare has become one of India's largest sectors both in terms of revenue & employment. The industry is growing at a tremendous pace owing to its strengthening coverage, services and increasing expenditure by public as well private players. Indian healthcare delivery system is categorised into two major components - public and private. The Government, i.e. public healthcare system comprises limited secondary and tertiary care institutions in key cities and focuses on providing basic healthcare facilities in the form of primary healthcare centres (PHCs) in rural areas. The private sector provides a majority of secondary, tertiary and quaternary care institutions with a major concentration in metros, tier I and tier-II cities. According to the data released by the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP), the Government of India, the hospital and diagnostic centres attracted Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) worth US\$ 4.83 billion between April 2000 and September 2017. Therefore the present study aims to study the FDI inflow in the Health Sector of India.

6. Methodology

The present research aims to study the Linkage between Health Expenditure and Foreign Direct Investment in India from 2000 to 2018. The objectives of the study are to provide the current status of FDI in health care and to identify some of the challenges and opportunities for Foreign Direct Investments in the healthcare sector. This study is based entirely on secondary data collected from various Government publications like reports of the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion, Indian Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF) and National Health Profile. After depicting the current condition of the healthcare industry in India, the researcher examines the level and pattern of flow of FDI in the healthcare sector in respect to Drugs and Pharmaceuticals, Hospitals and Diagnostic Centres, and Medical and Surgical Appliances as given in the DIPP report. The study is descriptive and based on the secondary data that is gathered from the books, various articles from journals, reports of the Department of Industrial Policy & Promotion and other valid online sources.

To analyze different determinants and parameters of FDI in the Health care sector in India, data on FDI in the Health care sector was taken from 2000 up to 2018.

This study is based on secondary data. For the present research work, the statistical data was collected mainly from secondary sources. Secondary sources include published and unpublished data collected from different organizations, institutes, agencies and government offices. Reputed journals were also used for collecting relevant information.

In the light of the objectives of our study, different explanatory and analytical statistical techniques were used to analyze the data relating to our study. For the interpretation of data, various statistical tools were used according to the requirement and suitability of the study. The data for the present study are collected from the website of the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion, Ministry of Commerce, Government of India. The collected data were analyzed by using statistical tools such as percentages, Mean, Standard Deviation and Co Efficient of Variance

7. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

This analysis is immensely helpful in marking comparative study of the changes in an item or groups of items over a while and to make conclusions regarding the date change. For this purpose, a base year is selected and the amount of the item – relating to the base year is taken equal to a hundred and Index numbers are computed for other years based on the number of items relating to the base years based on the amount of that item in those years.

8. Findings and Suggestions

75 % of foreign investors consider the prior permission route for selecting the suitable way of investing in India and 25% consider the automatic route of investment. 75% of investors prefer the urban area as an investment location in India. Semi-urban area considers 20 % and rural area 5%. The majority percentage (50%) of investors considers the best opportunities of FDI in Indian health care sectors are Hospitals. Health insurance considers 25% and technology-driven services are 25%. 75% of professionals give the favourable opinion regarding costs of the medical treatments is much lower in India than in other developed countries and 25 % professionals give the opinion against the costs of the medical treatments is much lower in India than in other developed countries. 75% of the professionals show a favourable opinion on the contribution of FDI in the Indian health care industry for Economic Development and 25% of the professionals show an unfavourable opinion on the contribution of FDI in the Indian health care industry for Economic Development. Among the 75% of professionals give the opinion on the inadequacy of existing healthcare infrastructure in India and 25% among all respondents, 90% of the professionals think that the FDI in Indian healthcare sectors generates the threats for the Indian businessman.

10% of the professionals think that the FDI in the Indian healthcare sectors will not generate threats for the Indian businessman. professionals give the opinion on the adequacy of existing healthcare infrastructure in India. The majority of the respondents (80%) of the general public think the FDI in the health care industry facilitates better services in the Indian healthcare industry. 20% of the respondents of the general public think the FDI in the health care industry cannot facilitate better services in the Indian healthcare industry. The huge benefits and concession granted by the government is the major factor for the flow of FDI in healthcare. The steady economic growth of the Indian economy and availability of raw materials through attracting FDI into India is not the major attractors of FDI in the healthcare sector. All the factors like remote diagnosis, monitoring and treatment of patients via videoconferencing or the internet and the establishment of telemedicine centres across the country by the government are the reason for the fast-emerging trend in Indian Telemedicine.

9. Conclusion

It is concluded that FDI plays a significant role in expanding the health care and tourism sector in India. There are many positive implications of foreign investment in the health care sector and medical tourism. One of the major impact foreign investment is the creation of the necessary infrastructure. Investments are also needed beyond the metros to expand access to healthcare. In addition to physical capacities in the health care sector, increasing the number of hospital beds, diagnostic facilities, and increasing the supply of speciality and super speciality centres, foreign investment can also help in raising the standards and quality of healthcare, in upgrading technology and in creating employment opportunities, with potential benefits to the health sector and the economy at large. This shows that appropriate policy to explore tourism resources and plans to develop new tourist venues and facilities may need to be considered to meet the increasing demand of tourism and its products in India expected as a result of continued strong foreign direct investment.

There are many medical devices, diagnostics, and e-Health. One major impact foreign investment would positive implications of foreign investment in hospitals and other healthcare services especially have is the creation of the necessary infrastructure. Investments are also needed beyond the metropolitan areas to expand access to healthcare. In addition to helping increase physical capacity in the healthcare sector (such as increasing the number of hospital beds, diagnostic facilities, and increasing the supply of speciality and super-speciality centres), foreign investment can also help in raising the standards and quality of healthcare, in upgrading technology, and in creating employment opportunities, with potential benefits to the health sector and the economy at large. However, the cost of medical care should be affordable most importantly in Tier 2 and Tier 3 locations.

Acknowledgement

We hereby declare that there has not been any funding from any agency for this research study.

References

- Dunning, JH (1988).** The eclectic paradigm of international production: A restatement and some possible extensions. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 19, 1–31.
- Outreville, JF (1998).** The health insurance sector: Market segmentation and international trade in health services. In UNCTAD–WHO joint publication, *International Trade in Health Services: A Development Perspective*. UNCTAD–WHO Geneva.
- Chanda, R (2001).** Trade-in health services. Commission on Macroeconomics and Health WHO, Geneva.
- Adlung, R and A Carzaniga (2002).** Health Services under the General Agreement on Trade in Services. In N Drager and C Vieira (eds.), *Trade in Health Services: Global, Regional, and Country Perspectives*, PAHO, Washington, DC.
- McPake, B (2002).** The globalisation of health sector reform policies. In *Health Policy in a Globalising World*, K Lee, S Buse and K Fustukian (eds.). United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Drager, N and C Vieira (eds.) (2002).** *Trade-in Health Services: Global, Regional, and Country Perspectives*. PAHO, Washington, DC.
- Chanda, R (2002a).** Trade-in health services. *Bulletin of the World Health Organisation*, 80, 158–163. WHO, Geneva.
- Chanda, R (2002b).** Trade-in health services. Paper presented at Assessment of GATS and Trade in Health Services: An International Consultation on Monitoring and Research Priorities. WHO, Geneva, January 9–11, <http://www.who.int/health-services-trade/>.
- Chanda, R (2002c).** Trade-in health services. In N Drager and C Vieira (eds.) *Trade-in Health Services: Global, Regional and Country Perspectives*. Washington, DC: IDAHO. Centre for Monitoring the Indian Economy (2006). Prowess database (www.cmie.com/database) CMIE, Mumbai.
- Smith, R (2004).** Foreign direct investment and trade in health services: A review of the literature. *Social Science and Medicine*, 59, 2313–23
- Blouin, C, N Drager and R Smith (eds.) (2006).** *International Trade in Health Services and the GATS*. World Bank, Washington, DC.
- Dutta, R (2006).** Bangalore's new USP: Healthcare. *Express Healthcare Management*. Indian Express Newspapers Mumbai, September. <http://www.expresshealthcaremgmt.com/200609/bangalorediscovered01.shtml>. 142 R. Chanda

CRISIL Research (2007). Hospitals: Annual Review. Industry Information Service, CRISIL Mumbai, February.

FICCI–Ernst & Young (2007). Opportunities in Healthcare: Destination India. New Delhi. India Brand Equity Foundation. www.ibef.org.

Outreville, JF (2007). Foreign direct investment in the health care sector and most-favoured locations in developing countries. *European Journal of Health Economics*, 8, 305–312.

Reserve Bank of India (2007). Note on foreign investments in India, Mumbai, April 1.

Peters, D and VR Muraleedharan (2008). Regulating India's health services: To what end? What future? *Social Science and Medicine*, 66, 2133–2144.

Sharma, A (2008). Needed: Lots of patience, Indian hospitals are learning to grow healthy. *Outlook India*. <http://www.outlookindia.com/article.aspx?238340>.

Shalini Aggarwal et.al, “Foreign Direct Investment in India”, *International Journal of Computational Engineering and Management*, Vol. 15, Issue 5, Sept. 2012.

Jasbir Singh et.al, “Role of Foreign Direct Investment in India: An Analytical Study”, *Research Inventory: International Journal of Engineering and Science*, Vol. 1, Issue 5, October 2012.

Urmila Patil (2013) “To study the trends in FDI in different sectors in India”, *International Journal of Scientific Research*, Vol. 2, Issue 11.

Renuka Sagar et.al, “Sectoral Trends and patterns of FDI in India”, *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services and Management Research*, Vol. 2, No. 7, July 2013.

M.Shahul Hameedu et.al, “Foreign Direct Investment, the Indian scenario”, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 4, Issue 2, February 2014.